

Protocol for a case-control study on risk factors for introduction of highly pathogenic avian influenza into holdings with poultry and other captive birds in Denmark

Helene Ane Jensen¹ (helene.jensen@sund.ku.dk), Anette Ella Boklund¹ (anebo@sund.ku.dk), Carsten Thure Kirkeby¹ (ckir@sund.ku.dk), Lene Jung Kjær¹ (lenju@sund.ku.dk), Charlotte Kristiane Hjulsager² (ckhj@ssi.dk), Lars Erik Larsen¹ (lael@sund.ku.dk), Søren Saxmose Nielsen¹ (saxmose@sund.ku.dk)

¹Department of Veterinary and Animal Sciences, University of Copenhagen (UCPH)

²Statens Serum Institut (SSI), Copenhagen

1 Background

Highly pathogenic avian influenza (HPAI) is an infectious and notifiable disease in poultry and other captive birds. The disease has a high mortality in avian species, and there is a risk for viral mutations with zoonotic potential, making the disease relevant to both animal and human health. Upon the detection of HPAI, all poultry or other captive birds in a holding are culled by the Danish Veterinary and Food Administration (DVFA). Since 2023, more than 130.000 poultry and other captive birds have died due to HPAI outbreaks in Denmark, and over 160 wild birds have tested positive to the virus (DVFA, 2023). Additionally, following an outbreak of HPAI in poultry, an affected country may lose its HPAI-free status in the EU and within the World Organisation for Animal Health (WOAH) leading to economic consequences for the poultry industry in the affected country.

The use of biosecurity measures may be able to reduce the risk for HPAI introduction. The term biosecurity is defined in the EU Animal Health Law (Regulation (EU) 2016/429) and may include limitation of access to the holding, proper sanitation, practising good hygiene and managing rodents (potential vectors of disease). After an outbreak of HPAI, the veterinary authorities do follow-up epidemiological investigations aiming to determine potential introduction routes and transmission. However, it is often not possible to determine the exact route of introduction. Previous studies have suggested that different landscape types (wetlands and coastal areas) may increase the risk for transmission of HPAI due to the presence of waterfowl and migrating birds (Kjær et al., 2022; Walsh et al., 2020), however, there is a knowledge gap concerning the introduction of the virus into holdings with poultry and other captive birds.

The study is relevant to different stakeholders including owners of poultry and other captive birds, advisors, risk assessors, and risk managers. The potential benefits are that decision-makers may be able to apply mitigating measures based on the study findings to reduce the risk for introduction of HPAI into poultry and other captive bird holdings. Additionally, the study may provide a further understanding of the transmission pathways of HPAI, and the findings could be used in epidemiological models aiming to predict HPAI outbreaks. From a societal point of view, disease control is relevant for public health due to the zoonotic potential of HPAI and for the poultry industry due to the economic consequences following an outbreak of the disease.

Part of the information on the source population is provided by the DVFA and other parts of the information are retrieved from the Central Husbandry Register (CHR), which is a publicly available database. A limiting factor is the number of HPAI outbreaks, which may result in a small sample size and affect the representability of the study. Two student assistants are employed to help recruit participants and interview the study population. Data are collected from March to December 2023. The plan is to publish the study in a scientific journal.

2 Purpose, Objectives and Hypothesis

2.1 Purpose of the study

The purpose of the study is to improve disease control of HPAI by providing evidence on the risk factors for HPAI introduction. This evidence may be useful for decision-makers and researchers within the fields of epidemiology and risk assessment.

2.2 Objectives

The objective of the study is to assess potential risk factors for introduction of HPAI into poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark. More specifically, the objective is to compare the odds of

introduction of HPAI related to a range of potential risk factors, such as biosecurity measures, in poultry and other captive bird holdings with and without a history of HPAI detection in the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023. An additional objective is to identify reasons for non-participation in the source population.

2.3 Hypothesis

Overall, the hypothesis of the study is that the exposure to risk factors is more frequent in holdings with a history of HPAI detection compared to holdings without a history of HPAI detection. More specifically, the hypotheses for each variable in the study are specified in Table 1. Some questions are only directed towards commercial holdings, and in Table 1, these questions are followed by “commercial holdings” in parentheses.

Table 1. Overview of study variables, variable types and hypotheses linked to each study variable.

	Variable	Type of variable	Hypothesis
Holding characteristics	Number of birds	Discrete	The more poultry or other captive birds in the holding, the higher the number of susceptible animals and the bigger the need for a larger air intake, which can lead to a higher risk of HPAI introduction.
	Type of production	Nominal	Commercial holdings generally have more birds and a higher density of birds compared to hobby holdings. Therefore, commercial holdings have a higher risk for HPAI introduction. Conversely, some commercial holdings may implement more biosecurity measures than hobby holdings and such measures could serve as protective factors lowering the risk for HPAI introduction.
Buildings and surroundings	Number of houses/stables used (if more types of birds, number of houses per bird type is stated)	Discrete	More houses are associated with a higher number of birds, and therefore a higher risk for HPAI introduction due to higher density of birds.
	Age of birds in weeks (commercial holdings)	Discrete	Young birds are more susceptible to HPAI (Lee et al., 2023). Conversely, older and bigger birds, for example turkeys, could be more susceptible to HPAI due to a larger air intake and higher density.
	Access to outdoor areas (outdoor area with fixed roof, outdoor area with and without fixed roof, outdoor area without fixed roof, no) and forms of coverage if not covered by fixed roof (net, bird deterrent wire,	Nominal	Birds with outdoor access have a higher risk for HPAI infection through contact with wild birds.

	trees, no, "other"-option to specify)		
	Surroundings (open land, open land with trees around, forest area, urban or suburban area)	Nominal	The surroundings are associated with the presence and number of wild birds. Therefore, the surrounding area is associated with the risk for HPAI introduction.
Feeding and bedding	Feeding location (inside, outside under fixed roof, outside under other forms of coverage, outside without fixed roof or other forms of coverage)	Nominal	Feeding poultry and other captive birds outside may attract wild birds. Therefore, feeding outside is associated with an increased risk for HPAI infection.
	Feeding with leftovers or kitchen waste (never, daily, weekly, less often)	Ordinal	Feeding with leftovers is associated with an increased risk for HPAI introduction because a) leftovers may be contaminated with HPAI through contact with raw poultry meat, b) leftovers may attract vectors/rodents, which may introduce HPAI into the holding, and c) leftovers may attract wild birds that could be infected with HPAI.
	Storage of feed (in a silo, "other"-option to specify, do not know), straw, hay and other roughage (in a closed barn without access to wild birds, in closed plastic cover without access to wild birds, in a barn with open door/gate, covered, outside, do not know)	Nominal	Poor storage of feeding material is associated with increased risk for HPAI introduction because there may be an increased contact with potentially infected wild birds.
	Spillage of feed around closed silos	Dichotomous	Spillage of feed may attract wild birds and is therefore associated with increased risk for HPAI introduction.
	Storage of vehicles and tools for handling bedding and feed when not in use (inside with closed door, under roof or inside with open door, outside)	Ordinal	Vehicles and tools that are stored outside when they are not used are associated with an increased risk for HPAI introduction because they may become contaminated and introduce the virus into the holding.
	Personnel and visitors	Number of people working in the holding	Discrete
Instruction/education of personnel in biosecurity		Ordinal	Personnel that are not educated in biosecurity have a higher risk for introducing HPAI into the holding.

(commercial holdings; yes, no, some have, do not know)		
Presence of a separate room with clean/unclean zone before access to the holding (commercial holdings; yes, no)	Dichotomous	A cleaning procedure should reduce the occurrence of HPAI.
Use of separate room with clean/unclean zone before access to the holding (commercial holdings; yes, no)	Dichotomous	
Biosecurity measures before access to the holding (commercial holdings; quarantine, shower, change of clothes and/or footwear, handwashing, disinfection of hands and/or footwear, use of mask, "other"-option to specify)	Nominal	
Written instructions regarding biosecurity (commercial holdings; pictograms, checklists, written material, no, "other"-option to specify)	Nominal	The more the personnel are informed about biosecurity (e.g., cleaning procedures), the lower the risk for HPAI introduction.
Challenges in communication to and between personnel (commercial holdings; often, sometimes, no, do not know)	Ordinal	Holdings with challenges in communication to and between personnel have a higher risk for HPAI introduction as biosecurity measures may not be communicated clearly.
Number of languages spoken to and between personnel (commercial holdings)	Discrete	Some information on biosecurity protocols may be lost in translation in a multilingual environment. Therefore, the risk for HPAI introduction is increased when more languages are spoken to and between personnel.
Change in personnel (yes, no)	Dichotomous	Holdings that have frequent changes in personnel have a higher risk for HPAI introduction because new workers may be less aware of biosecurity protocols in the holding. Additionally, the number of potentially infectious contacts is increased.
Frequency of visits from a veterinarian	Discrete	The veterinarian may be able to advise the owner on biosecurity measures that could reduce the risk for HPAI introduction. Therefore, frequent visits from the veterinarian could be associated with a lower risk for HPAI introduction. Conversely, the veterinarian may carry pathogens

			from another holding, which may increase the risk for HPAI introduction.
	Frequency of visitors in the holding (never, weekly, 1-3 times per month, less often, do not know)	Ordinal	A high frequency of visitors and movements in and out of the holding increase the risk for HPAI introduction because the number of potentially infectious contacts is increased.
Ventilation	Heating of buildings/houses with poultry or other captive birds in certain periods (yes, in the following months ...; yes, from the birds arrive until ...; no; do not know)	Nominal	Heating the buildings during certain periods may create an unfavorable environment for the virus and reduce the risk for HPAI occurrence.
	Type of ventilation system (negative pressure ventilation, neutral pressure ventilation, natural ventilation, "other"-option to specify)	Nominal	Ventilation systems have an impact on the indoor air quality and exchange of air. The ventilation may contribute to the circulation of virus, e.g., through contact with infected wild birds or droppings. Therefore, holdings with poor ventilation have an increased risk for HPAI introduction through airborne transmission.
	Location of air inlet/outlet (roof, wall, ceiling, "other"-option to specify)	Nominal	The risk for HPAI introduction is different in holdings with ventilation through the roof compared to holdings with ventilation through the walls or ceiling because the contact with potentially infected wild birds (e.g., infected droppings) is different.
	Protection of air inlet/outlet	Nominal	Protection of air inlet/outlet lowers the risk for HPAI introduction due to protection against contact with potentially infected wild birds and their droppings.
Wild birds	Presence of crops, lakes, coastal areas, wetlands or anything else on or around the holding that may attract wild birds	Dichotomous	The presence of wild birds and surroundings that attract wild birds are associated with a higher risk for HPAI introduction into the holding.
	Frequency of observations of geese, ducks or swans near the buildings on the property (within <20 m and <500 m, respectively; never, sporadic/few days, seasonal, often/all year), approximate abundance (0, a few, hundreds, thousands) and their location	Observations of wild birds: Ordinal Abundance: Ordinal	The presence of wild birds is associated with a higher risk for HPAI introduction into the holding. Geese, ducks, swans and gulls are more likely to be infected with HPAI, and therefore their presence around the holding is associated with a higher risk for HPAI introduction.
	Frequency of observations of gulls near the buildings on the property (within <20 m and <500	Location: Nominal	

	m, respectively; never, sporadic/few days, seasonal, often/all year), approximate abundance (0, a few, hundreds, thousands) and their location		
	Frequency of observations of other wild birds within <500 m of the property (never, sporadic/few days, seasonal, often/all year), approximate abundance (0, a few, hundreds, thousands) and their location		
	Use of deterrents against wild birds	Nominal	Use of deterrents against wild birds lowers the risk for HPAI introduction.
Rodents	Load of mice and rats on the property (scale 1-5)	Ordinal	A high load of mice and rats on the property is associated with a higher risk for HPAI introduction into the holding because rodents may serve as mechanical vectors.
Trade of poultry and their products	Frequency of collection of poultry for slaughter, eggs, dead birds (collected by DAKA) or delivery of poultry to other holdings (daily, weekly, 1-3 times per month, less often, do not know)	Ordinal	The increased movement of poultry in connection with slaughtering, collection of eggs or dead birds, or delivery of poultry to other holdings is associated with an increased risk for HPAI transmission.
	Method of capturing poultry for slaughter (manually with own personnel, manually with external personnel, by machine)	Nominal	The risk for HPAI introduction is different in holdings where poultry are captured manually compared to holdings where poultry are captured using a machine.
	Emptying of entire houses in connection with slaughter or delivery of poultry to other holdings (yes, no)	Dichotomous	Emptying entire houses in relation to slaughtering is associated with a decreased risk for HPAI introduction.
	Frequency of new poultry arriving in the holding, and delivery and allocation of feed and bedding (daily, 2-3 times per week, weekly, 1-3 times per month, less often, never, do not know)	Ordinal	Frequent introduction of new animals and frequent deliveries of feed and bedding are associated with an increased risk for HPAI introduction.
	Frequency of collection of dead birds by DAKA (daily, weekly, 1-3 times per month, less often, never, do not know)	Ordinal	A frequent collection of dead birds lowers the risk for HPAI transmission.

3 Populations

3.1 Study unit

The study unit is the individual holding containing poultry or other captive birds. In this study, re-infection of individual holdings is not possible, as each holding is included only once. For more information, please refer to Section 5.2 on eligibility criteria.

3.2 Target population

The target population is poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark and potentially similar holdings in other countries.

3.3 Study population

The study population consists of recorded holdings with poultry and other captive birds in Denmark with and without a history of HPAI detection in the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022 and 2022/2023 with owners that have agreed to participate in the study.

4 Study design

The study is carried out as a case-control study. Poultry and other captive bird holdings that had outbreaks of HPAI in the considered epidemiological seasons serve as cases, and for each case, two controls are matched on the number of birds in the holding, type(s) of birds in the holding (turkeys, ducks and geese, pheasants, chicken (broilers or layers), or a mix of *Anseriformes* and *Galliformes*) and shortest distance from the holding to coastal areas or wetlands (categorised). We interview the owners of the study population with questions related to potential risk factors (Table 1).

5 Participation

5.1 Source of study units – Study population

The DVFA provides information about previous outbreak holdings. The study population is an approximate proxy for the target population because it potentially includes all Danish poultry and other captive bird holdings with HPAI outbreaks in the considered epidemiological seasons (that is, all outbreak holdings where the owners wish to participate in the study). We retrieved information about potential control holdings from the CHR.

5.2 Inclusion/exclusion criteria for participation

Poultry and other captive bird holdings are eligible for inclusion as cases in the study if they had a primary outbreak of HPAI during the epidemiological seasons 2020/2021, 2021/2022, 2022/2023. I.e., holdings with secondary outbreaks (outbreaks that are epidemiologically linked to a previous outbreak) of HPAI are excluded. We exclude secondary outbreaks because the DVFA and DK-VET have already determined the route of introduction through epidemiological investigations. If a holding had more than one primary outbreak in the considered epidemiological seasons, we will only include the most recent outbreak as a case. The matched holdings with poultry and other captive birds are eligible if they 1) are registered in CHR, 2) had no previous HPAI outbreaks in the considered epidemiological seasons according to the DVFA, and 3) are located on the mainland of Denmark or bridged islands. We exclude holdings located on non-bridged islands due to time and budget constraints.

5.3 Selection of control holdings

For each case, we select ten potential matched controls from the CHR. The data collectors contact owners of outbreak holdings from the source population and matched potential control holdings are contacted in groups of ten starting from the top (if none of the ten possible controls wish to participate, the data collectors are provided with another list of the next ten possible controls).

6 Data management

6.1 Variables

6.1.1 Outcome variables

The outcome variable of the study is dichotomous and is the classification of cases (i.e., holdings with a history of HPAI detection) and controls (i.e., holdings without a history of HPAI detection).

6.1.2 Explanatory variables

The data consist of discrete, ordinal, nominal and dichotomous variables. The potential risk factors cover characteristics of the holding, buildings and surroundings, feeding and bedding practices, personnel and visitors, biosecurity measures, ventilation, observations of wild birds and rodents, and trade of poultry and their products. For the type of each variable, please refer to Table 1.

6.2 Data collection

We collect data primarily through questionnaire-based interviews of the owners during a visit to their holding. If the owner of a previous outbreak holding (case) is not interested in having visitors, the owner can be interviewed by telephone. As a third option, and if the owner is not interested in neither a visit nor a telephonic interview, the questionnaire can be sent by e-mail for the owner to fill out and return to the interviewer. The three options are listed and used in prioritized order and a visit to the holding is the first choice as some questions are answered by observation. However, Options 2 and 3 may be relevant if the case owner has moved away from the holding or if the owner no longer has poultry or other captive birds. For the control holdings, only Options 1 and 2 are possible. Informed consent is a requirement before proceeding with the data collection. We obtain owner consent in either written or oral form depending on whether the owner is interviewed in person, by telephone or e-mail.

Two student assistants and the first author collect data from March to December 2023. Before the start of data collection, the data collectors have trained the questionnaire-based interview in a holding that is not included in the study population.

6.3 Database construction and handling

All questions are in a questionnaire on paper and online in SurveyXact (Rambøll Management Consulting, Aarhus, Denmark). The interviewers fill out the questionnaire on paper or directly in SurveyXact on a tablet during the interview. If the questionnaire is filled out on paper, the interviewer subsequently types the answers into SurveyXact. We import the data as an Excel (Microsoft, Redmond, WA, USA) file in one table with one row for each study unit and columns for each question/variable. The first author is responsible for keeping the data on a secured H-drive at UCPH servers.

6.4 Data control and editing

The first author proofreads the data. In case of missing, extreme, or illegal values (i.e., negative values for discrete variables listed in Table 1) in the dataset, the first author contacts the interviewers to see if they recall the information. Secondly, we may contact the holding owners if they have given consent to this.

6.5 Data processing for statistical analysis

When extracting the dataset from SurveyXact, all questions are stated in columns. These may be processed with shorter names for the statistical analysis (e.g., a question and column headline such as “How would you describe the load of rodents on the property on a scale from 1 to 5?” may be renamed to “Rodents”). Depending on whether the dataset contains free-text answers and “other”-categories, these would have to be processed for statistical analysis as well. We will avoid changing the original dataset. The first author is responsible for this part with support from the co-authors.

7 Statistical analysis

7.1 Sample size calculations

The entire source population of cases is potentially included. For every included case, two controls are matched. We expect that potential risk factors for introduction of HPAI are identified with a minimum detectable odds ratio of 4.5 based on an *a priori* power calculation with the following assumptions: Sample size of 72 holdings (24 cases and 48 controls), prevalence of exposure to potential risk factors in control holdings on 20%, confidence level of 95%, and power of 80%.

7.2 Descriptive analysis

We will describe the variables of interest stratified by cases and controls. The discrete variables such as number of birds in the holding and number of houses/stables are described and summarized by means, medians and ranges. The ordinal, nominal and dichotomous variables such as load of rodents on the property (scale of 1-5), type of birds (turkeys, ducks and geese, pheasants, chicken (broilers or layers), or a mix of *Anseriformes* and *Galliformes*) and spillage of feed around closed silos (yes/no), respectively, are described and summarized by proportions and frequencies.

7.3 Statistical analysis

We will analyse data using logistic analysis comparing cases and controls. Results are reported as odds ratios with 95% confidence intervals. In the univariable analysis, we will use the likelihood ratio test, and statistically significant variables are identified using a 20% level of significance and the 95% confidence interval. Statistically significant variables are included in the multivariable analysis. We will use the Akaike Information Criterion to determine variable selection using a forward inclusion strategy. We will test variables for confounding by assessing changes in the parameter estimates by including potentially confounding variables in the model. However, due to the small sample size, it may not be possible to fully control for confounding, and the analyses may be limited to univariable analyses. Some confounding is minimized by matching cases and controls on the size of the holding, type of birds and shortest distance from the holding to coastal areas or wetlands. The first author will do the analyses with support from the co-authors. We analyse the data in R (version 4.3.1, R Core Team, Vienna, Austria).

8 Validity, Bias and Uncertainty

8.1 External validity: Selection bias

The source population of cases potentially includes all Danish outbreak holdings in the considered epidemiological seasons. The source population of controls only contains holdings that are registered in CHR, and these are not necessarily representative of the unregistered holdings. However, we presume that many of the unregistered holdings are hobby/backyard holdings with few poultry or other captive birds.

Non-participation may be due to negative attitudes towards the contingency work at the DVFA and/or potential consequences of the study findings. Non-participants may differ significantly from participants, and this could affect the representativity of the study population. We will state the response rate when reporting the study findings.

If the target population is extended beyond poultry and other captive bird holdings in Denmark, this may introduce further selection bias and reduce the representativity of the sample leading to an over- or underestimation of the results.

8.2 Internal validity: Information bias

Recall bias may be present in the study because owners who experienced HPAI outbreaks in their holding in 2020 may not remember details as clearly as owners who experienced HPAI outbreaks in their holding in 2023. Furthermore, owners of outbreak holdings might have spent time already trying to find reasons for the outbreak in their holding, and therefore recall that period better than owners of a holding without a previous outbreak. Additionally, as the study data are based on a questionnaire-based interview, there is a risk of response bias (e.g., because of liability concerns). This is minimised by assuring the owners that all data will be anonymised and, in the holdings visited, by additional observations in the holding. Moreover, all potential exposures may not be covered in the questionnaire.

Misclassification bias may be present if a control holding was infected with HPAI at some point in the considered epidemiological seasons, but the owner was not aware that the birds had been infected with HPAI or did not report the suspicion to a veterinarian or the DVFA. This may result in some cases not being detected. We expect that HPAI is spread within holdings with a high mortality and clear clinical signs. However, clinical signs may have been minor if the holding was already co-infected with low pathogenic avian influenza virus.

Blinding is not carried out; the owners, the interviewers and the researchers are aware of the holding's history of HPAI outbreaks in the considered epidemiological seasons. This may introduce bias, e.g., interviewer bias, if the interviewers treat owners of case and control holdings differently. For example, the risk may be high in questions with grading, e.g., of the load of rodents or abundance of wild birds. The risk may be low in factual questions related to the size of the holding, type of birds and type of ventilation system. This potential bias is reduced by asking all owners the same pre-formulated questions with minor changes depending on whether the holding is a case or control, and the interviewers have practised the interview questions in a test holding not included in the study.

8.3 Internal validity: Confounding bias

There may be several confounders among the variables mentioned in Table 1. Some confounding is minimized by matching the cases and controls. However, it may not be possible to fully control for confounding due to the small sample size.

8.4 Internal validity: Loss to follow-up

Former owners of poultry and other captive birds are lost to follow-up (e.g. if they have ceased their production).

8.5 Analyses

Using the statistical methods described in Section 7.3, we compare the cases and controls to assess the objectives of the study. Due to the small sample size, the study may be limited to univariable analyses, and the sample size might not be sufficient to stratify for confounders. The handling of missing values is described in Section 6.4.

8.6 Selective reporting

We will report all results (significant and non-significant) to safeguard against selective reporting. Reporting bias is also reduced by having questions pre-formulated in a questionnaire.

8.7 Other biases or uncertainties

There may be a temporal effect in the study: The legislative measures implemented by the DVFA change over time depending on the risk picture. This is something that may act as a confounder as it reduces the risk of HPAI introduction and increases public awareness of biosecurity measures (i.e., keeping birds under roof and/or hygiene measures before entering the holding). However, information about the outdoor access in the holding is already accounted for in the questions regarding outdoor access and coverage. Additionally, over time, there may be increased attention on HPAI due to its detection in non-avian species (mammals) which may affect the behaviours of owners of poultry and other captive birds.

9 Impact assessment: Limitations of the study and overall uncertainty

As mentioned in the previous sections, the study contains limitations in terms of a small sample size, self-selection bias, information bias (recall bias), and confounding bias.

Due to the small sample size, the study might be limited to univariable analysis, and the sample size may not be sufficient to stratify for confounders. We reduce the confounding bias by matching the cases and controls on the size of the holding, type of birds and shortest distance to wetlands and coastal areas. We minimise information bias by using a pre-formulated questionnaire and by interviewers training to do the interview before data collection. Regarding the changes in legislative measures over time, information about these should be collected from historic national orders for the final article. However, housing orders may often already be effectuated by the time of the outbreaks and therefore it may be difficult to assess the effects of legislative measures. Additionally, we take the information about the outdoor access in the holding into account in the questions regarding outdoor access and coverage.

Based on the presentation of potential biases in the previous sections, we expect the overall risk of bias to be low or moderate. This is because 1) the methods used are appropriate to the case-control

study design and the research question, and 2) potential biases are considered to the extent possible during the analyses.

As long as the potential biases, limitations and uncertainties mentioned above are addressed and discussed transparently, this study should be able to provide valuable information on how HPAI is introduced into poultry and other captive bird holdings; a knowledge gap that needs to be elucidated to improve disease control. Additionally, the study can be compared to similar studies in other populations to reduce statistical uncertainties.

10 Ethical considerations

10.1 Study approval

The processing of personal data was approved by The Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences (reference ID 3121665/4242) at the University of Copenhagen, and The Research Ethics Committee for Faculty of Health and Medical Sciences found the study compliant with relevant Danish and International standards and guidelines for research ethics (case no. 504-0394/23-5000).

10.2 Confidentiality and anonymity

Data are anonymized to the extent possible as soon as possible after finalization of data collection. Data enabling re-identification will during the study be kept by the first author on a secured H-drive at UCPH servers.

10.3 Authorship and publication rights

Authorship follows the “Vancouver rules” (ICMJE, n.d.). The University of Copenhagen owns the data post-study.

11 References

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